

Utility of Coupling Microwave-derived Soil Moisture and Radiometric Surface Temperature in an Energy Balance Modeling Scheme

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Abstract—Over the last several years a Two-Source (soil + vegetation) Energy Balance (TSEB) modeling scheme has been developed and tested using either microwave-derived near-surface soil moisture (TSEB_{SM}) or radiometric surface temperature (TSEB_{TR}) as the key surface boundary condition. Output of the surface heat fluxes from both schemes are compared using microwave and radiometric surface temperature observations collected during the 1997 Southern Great Plains experiment (SGP97) conducted in Oklahoma, USA. Results from the heat flux comparisons and simulated versus observed surface temperatures suggest revisions to the TSEB_{SM} scheme are needed to better constrain flux predictions from the soil and vegetation in order to accommodate a wider range of environmental conditions. The revisions involve an adjustment to the soil evaporation algorithm for ‘decoupling’ effects and assimilation of the Priestley-Taylor coefficient estimated from the TSEB_{TR} model.

I. INTRODUCTION

Both the TSEB_{TR} and the TSEB_{SM} models have been applied to remotely sensed data collected during SGP97 and have been validated using tower and aircraft-based flux observations. For TSEB_{TR}, TIMS (Thermal Infrared Multi-spectral Scanner) data at high resolution (~12 m pixel) have been used by [1], while for TSEB_{SM}, the L-band ESTAR (Electronically Scanned Thinned Array Radiometer) near-surface soil moisture (~0-5 cm layer) product at 800 m pixel resolution has been applied in [2]. Results of the comparisons with flux observations suggest the models provide acceptable estimates. However, tower-based fluxes represent a very small fraction of the land surface, while aircraft-based fluxes represent regional averages. Hence it is nearly impossible to validate the spatial patterns in heat fluxes produced by such models.

For one day, (Day 183, July 2, 1997) both TIMS and ESTAR data were collected during the same midmorning period (~1630 UTC) over the El Reno study site. This provided a unique opportunity to compare output from both two-source models for the same region on a pixel-by-pixel basis, with the TIMS radiometric surface temperature, T_R , aggregated to the same 800 m pixel resolution as the ESTAR data. In addition, since TSEB_{SM} also simulates an effective surface temperature, T_{surf} , these estimates could be compared to T_R observed from TIMS, providing additional information for evaluating TSEB_{SM} parameterizations.

II. METHODOLOGY

Both the TSEB_{TR} and the TSEB_{SM} models use the land surface-transfer scheme developed by [3]. A resistance network for the vegetation and soil components is utilized based on the approximation that the radiometric and effective surface temperature is comprised of mean canopy, T_C , and soil, T_S , component temperatures,

$$T_{surf} \approx T_R \approx (f_c T_C^4 + (1-f_c) T_S^4)^{1/4} \quad (1)$$

where the fractional vegetation cover, f_c , is estimated from a ‘normalized’ Normalized-Difference-Vegetation-Index (NDVI) as derived by [4]. The sensible heat flux from the canopy, H_C , and soil, H_S , are initially estimated using the following relations,

$$\begin{aligned} H_C &= \rho C_p \frac{T_C - T_{AC}}{R_B} = \left(1 - f_G \alpha_{PT} \left[\frac{\Delta}{\Delta + \gamma} \right] \right) R_{N,c} \\ H_S &= \rho C_p \frac{T_S - T_{AC}}{R_S} \\ H &= H_C + H_S = \rho C_p \frac{T_{AC} - T_A}{R_A} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where ρ is the air density, C_p is the heat capacity of air, α_{PT} is the Priestley-Taylor parameter set equal to 1.3 [5] for the green part of the canopy, Δ is the slope of the saturation vapor pressure-temperature curve at T_C , γ is the psychrometric constant, and f_G is the fraction of canopy that is ‘green’ or actively transpiring, which may be obtained from knowledge of the phenology of the vegetation. The net radiation of the canopy, $R_{N,c}$, is estimated from a radiation extinction model evaluating shortwave and longwave exchanges within the canopy layer [6]. The resistances R_B , R_S and R_A are the total boundary layer resistance of the complete canopy of leaves, the soil surface resistance and the aerodynamic resistance to heat transfer from canopy air space temperature, T_{AC} , to the surface layer temperature, T_A , respectively; formulas are described in [3]. The Priestley-Taylor formulation only provides an initial calculation, and it can be overridden to accommodate a wider range of environmental conditions [3]. An iteration procedure has been recently developed by [7] and [8] which will adjust the α_{PT} value until T_C and T_S estimates used in Eq. (1) agree with the measured T_R .

For TSEB_{SM} a similar set of expressions are used, except the soil surface latent heat flux is solved directly from the expression,

$$LE_s = \frac{\rho C_p h_r e_s(T_s) - e_{ac}}{\gamma R_{sv} + R_s} \quad (3)$$

where the resistance R_{sv} represents the soil resistance to water vapor transfer within the soil layer and is estimated from an exponential expression relating R_{sv} to the ratio of actual to saturated soil water content of the near-surface (0-5 cm layer) [9]. The parameter $e_s(T_s)$ is the saturation vapor pressure at soil surface temperature T_s , e_{ac} is the vapor pressure in the canopy air space, and h_r is the relative humidity of the soil layer computed from the surface soil water content using the method described by [10]. With the expression for H_s in (2) and taking soil heat flux as a fraction of net radiation at the soil surface (i.e., $G \approx 0.3R_{N,S}$) the soil surface energy balance (viz., $R_{N,S} - G - LE_s - H_s = 0$) can be satisfied yielding T_s . Then with T_c derived from the Priestley-Taylor formulation, this is used in deriving the effective surface temperature T_{surf} using (1) and the vapor pressure of the canopy surface, e_c required to achieve energy balance for the canopy layer (i.e., $R_{N,C} - H_C - LE_c = 0$) where

$$LE_c = \frac{\rho C_p e_{ac} - e_c}{\gamma R_b} \quad (4)$$

Unfortunately, adjusting α_{PT} for a wider range of environmental conditions is not as straight forward with the TSEB_{SM} scheme since (1) cannot be used to restrict the component temperatures. However, the model will not permit non-physical solutions, such as $LE_s < 0$ or condensation during the daytime. In this case, the Priestley-Taylor approximation is dropped, and several approximations are used [2].

III. RESULTS

Both the TSEB_{SM} and TSEB_{TR} schemes were run using half-hourly averaged meteorological data from the Mesonet network. From the same aircraft supporting TIMS, the Thematic Mapper Simulator (TMS) instrument provided similar resolution visible-near infrared imagery for creating an NDVI map for the area. Overlapping coverage for ESTAR and TIMS/TMS comprised an area approximately 6 km north-south by 20 km east-west, which was primarily composed of harvested winter wheat fields and grasslands used for grazing cattle. For more details concerning the processing of TIMS/TMS data see [1]. Both NDVI and T_R were aggregated to 800 m pixel resolution of ESTAR to allow pixel-by-pixel comparisons of output from TSEB_{TR} and TSEB_{SM} models.

Since the most significant discrepancies are with the turbulent fluxes, H and LE , these results will only be presented here. A pixel-by-pixel comparison of H and LE in Fig. 1 shows a fair amount of scatter having Root-Mean-Square-Difference (RMSD) of $\approx 60 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$ for H and LE . The area-average $\langle H \rangle$ from TSEB_{SM} $\approx 40 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$ lower and $\langle LE \rangle \approx 25 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ higher than estimated by TSEB_{TR} (Table 1). A comparison of T_{surf} from TSEB_{SM} with T_R from TIMS shows (Fig. 2) a bias ($\approx 2 \text{ K}$, see Table 1), with a RMSD $\approx 3 \text{ K}$.

Fig. 1. Comparison of H and LE between the original TSEB_{SM} model and the TSEB_{TR} scheme.

Fig. 2. Comparison of T_{surf} from the original TSEB_{SM} formulation versus T_R from TIMS.

TABLE I. Comparison of area average sensible and latent heat fluxes from the two models and TSEB_{SM} simulated versus remotely sensed (radiometric) surface temperature.

Model	$\langle H \rangle$ (W m^{-2})	$\langle LE \rangle$ (W m^{-2})	$\langle T_{surf} \rangle$ (C)
TSEB _{TR}	119	374	40.1*
Original TSEB _{SM}	77	400	38.1
Revised TSEB _{SM}	113	351	40.3

* $\langle T_R \rangle$ from the TIMS observations

Previous studies, [2] and [11], comparing T_{surf} simulated by TSEB_{SM} with T_R show similar scatter, albeit without a significant bias. The fact that $\langle T_{surf} \rangle$ is less than $\langle T_R \rangle$ is not surprising since T_R is affected by surface moisture conditions whereas the TSEB_{SM} formulation uses an integrated soil moisture value for

the 0-5 cm depth. In fact, [12] using a soil profile model show a significant ‘decoupling’ between surface soil moisture (≈ 0.5 cm) and the moisture at 5 cm as the soil dries suggesting that the soil surface energy balance becomes more strongly coupled to surface moisture conditions than at deeper layers as the soil dries.

An attempt to account for the effect of decoupling in the soil evaporation formulation (3) was made by adjusting the relative humidity in the pore space, h_R , since $h_R \sim 1$ until the moisture is well below field capacity [10]. The adjustment was simply to multiply h_R in (3) by the ratio of the ESTAR-derived soil moisture, W , to the field capacity, W_{FC} , based on soil texture information following [13]. In addition, since the TSEB_{SM} scheme cannot easily adjust α_{pT} , the TSEB_{TR} estimate of α_{pT} for each pixel was used (i.e., assimilated) by TSEB_{SM}.

The effect of these two revisions in the TSEB_{SM} output of the fluxes and T_{surf} is significant (Fig. 3 and 4). The agreement between the two model estimates has improved (Fig. 3) with RMSD for H reduced to ≈ 40 W m⁻²; RMSD remains at ≈ 60 Wm⁻² for LE , but there is better overall agreement between the two model estimates (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Comparison of H and LE between the revised TSEB_{SM} model and the TSEB_{TR} scheme.

On an area-average basis, $\langle H \rangle$ from the revised TSEB_{SM} is within 10 W m⁻² of the TSEB_{TR} estimate and $\langle LE \rangle$ is within ≈ 20 W m⁻² of the TSEB_{TR} value (Table 1). In addition, the pixel-by-pixel comparison of T_{surf} simulated by TSEB_{SM} with T_R from TIMS shows virtually no bias (Table 1) and a RMSD ≈ 3 K (Fig. 4).

The results only revising (3) to address the effects of ‘decoupling’ in the TSEB_{SM} scheme yielded a similar comparison between simulated T_{surf} and T_R from TIMS. However, there were larger discrepancies in the heat fluxes between the two models; RMSD for H and LE were higher at ≈ 55 W m⁻² and ≈ 70 Wm⁻², respectively.

Fig. 4. Comparison of T_{surf} from the revised TSEB_{SM} formulation versus T_R from TIMS.

The spatial patterns of H and LE from TSEB_{SM} and TSEB_{TR} models are illustrated in Fig. 5. There is general agreement in the spatial distributions of the heat fluxes, except for an area located near the center of the image, which has significantly lower H and higher LE estimated by TSEB_{SM}. Factors contributing to this discrepancy are under investigation.

Fig. 5. Spatial patterns of H and LE from the revised TSEB_{SM} model and the TSEB_{TR} scheme.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This preliminary analysis comparing output on a spatially distributed manner from two land-atmosphere transfer schemes (TSEB) linked to different remotely sensed boundary conditions provided a unique

opportunity to evaluate uncertainty in model flux estimates on a pixel-by-pixel basis. Moreover the TSEB_{SM} scheme, which is less able to consider a wider range of environmental conditions compared to the TSEB_{TR} formulation using radiometric surface temperature, is revised based on comparisons made with TSEB_{TR} output of the heat fluxes, and comparisons between the effective surface temperature T_{surf} simulated by TSEB_{SM} and T_R observations from TIMS. This led to the implementation of two revisions; one to the soil evaporation formulation (3) and the other to adopting α_{pT} values predicted by TSEB_{TR}. With both revisions being implemented, there is closer agreement in heat fluxes computed by the two models and better agreement between TSEB_{SM} simulated and radiometric surface temperature observations.

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